

ISic0476

Fragment

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Recorded by Mommsen in Agrigento civic museum in 1877

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---]PEIAI[---]

0. [---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

The fragment has not been located in recent times. It is a working assumption that it was transferred into the modern museum from the original collection of the civic museum and remains to be identified in the museum stores.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491701

EDR 142398

EDCS 21900536

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7195 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650772>)

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